

AI-Integrated Design and Optimization of Aceclofenac Loaded Transethosomal Gel

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Abstract

Objective:

This study focused on the development and evaluation of aceclofenac-loaded transethosomes for improved topical delivery, along with the application of artificial intelligence, particularly the Random Forest Regression (RFR) model, to predict and optimize formulation performance.

Methods:

Transethosomes containing aceclofenac were prepared using the thin-film hydration method with phosphatidylcholine, ethanol, and surfactants (Tween 80 and Span 80). The RFR algorithm was employed to establish a relationship between formulation variables and key responses such as entrapment efficiency (EE%) and cumulative drug release (CDR%). Drug-excipient compatibility was assessed using FT-IR analysis. The optimized vesicles were characterized for entrapment efficiency, particle size, zeta potential and morphology. The formulation was incorporated into a Carbopol 934 gel and evaluated for physicochemical properties and *In vitro* drug release. Stability studies were conducted to examine formulation integrity over time.

Results:

The optimized transethosomal gel showed nanoscale vesicles with good stability characteristics. The RFR model effectively predicted formulation behaviour and aided in selecting optimal parameters. FT-IR results indicated no significant interaction between the drug and excipients. The optimized formulation demonstrated an entrapment efficiency of 78.38% along with a controlled and sustained drug release pattern. Stability testing confirmed that the formulation maintained its properties throughout the study duration.

Conclusion:

The study successfully demonstrated that Random Forest Regression can be effectively utilized to optimize aceclofenac-loaded transethosomal formulations. The developed system showed desirable stability and sustained drug release, indicating its suitability for enhanced topical drug delivery.

Keywords: Aceclofenac, Transethosomes; Random Forest Regression; Artificial intelligence optimization; *In vitro* drug release

I. INTRODUCTION

Aceclofenac is a commonly prescribed non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) used to manage conditions such as rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, ankylosing spondylitis, and other musculoskeletal disorders [10]. While it possesses strong anti-inflammatory and pain-relieving properties, oral administration of aceclofenac is often linked to gastrointestinal side effects, including gastric irritation, dyspepsia, and ulceration [13]. These adverse effects are primarily due to systemic exposure and the inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis, which can hinder long-term treatment and reduce patient compliance [14]. As a result, alternative delivery methods that minimize systemic absorption while maintaining therapeutic effectiveness are of significant clinical interest [5].

Topical drug delivery presents a promising alternative by targeting the site of inflammation and reducing systemic side effects [5]. However, its effectiveness is limited by the stratum corneum's barrier function. To address this challenge, advanced vesicular systems such as transethosomes have been developed [12]. Transethosomes are ultra-deformable lipid vesicles made from phospholipids, ethanol, and an edge activator, which collectively enhance the flexibility of the vesicles and their ability to penetrate the skin [9]. Due to their high drug entrapment efficiency and improved dermal penetration [16], transethosomes represent a promising

carrier for topical and transdermal drug delivery [3]. Therefore, this study aimed to formulate and evaluate aceclofenac-loaded transethosomes to improve topical anti-inflammatory therapy.

Application of Machine Learning & Random Forest Regression in Formulation Optimization:

Machine learning-based regression was utilized to optimize aceclofenac-loaded transethosomal formulations because of its capacity to model nonlinear relationships and interactions among multiple variables [7]. The ensemble-based regression model achieved high predictive accuracy ($R^2 > 0.95$) for forecasting drug entrapment efficiency from key formulation variables [6]. This AI-assisted approach reduced the number of experimental trials and improved formulation efficiency, while also identifying the relative influence of formulation components on entrapment efficiency, underscoring its value in pharmaceutical formulation optimization [6-8].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Aceclofenac was obtained as a gift sample from Firstmed Therapeutics Pvt,Ltd.Phosphatidylcholine (Phospholipon 90G), Span 80, Tween 80, ethanol, chloroform, Carbopol 934, triethanolamine, and all other reagents and solvents used in the study were of analytical grade.

Methods

Preparation of Aceclofenac-Loaded Transethosomes

Aceclofenac-loaded transethosomes were prepared via thin film hydration with ethanol as a penetration enhancer. Phosphatidylcholine (Phospholipon® 90G), aceclofenac, and an edge activator (Span 80 or Tween 80) were dissolved in chloroform:methanol (2:1 v/v), evaporated to form a thin film, and hydrated with hydroethanolic phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The resulting vesicular dispersion was sonicated to reduce size and stored at 4 °C for further evaluation.

Table-1 Composition of Aceclofenac-Loaded Transethosomes

Component	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Aceclofenac (mg)	15	15	15	15	15	15
Phosphatidylcholine (mg)	60	60	60	60	60	60
Tween 80 (mg)	10	20	30	–	–	–
Span 80 (mg)	–	–	–	10	20	30
Ethanol (mL)	1	1	1	1	1	1

INPUT

Several Machine Learning (ML) algorithms can be applied depending on the objective

- Random Forest Regression (RFR)

Sample data extracted from the image

data = {

'Formulation': ['F1', 'F2', 'F3', 'F4', 'F5', 'F6'],

'Aceclofenac': [15, 15, 15, 15, 15, 15],

'Phosphatidylcholine': [60, 60, 60, 60, 60, 60],

'Tween 80': [10, 20, 30, 0, 0, 0],

'Span 80': [0, 0, 0, 10, 20, 30],

'Ethanol': [1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1],

'CDR_Percentage': [85, 88, 95, 89, 91,92] # Example CDR% values

OUTPUT

Initialize Random Forest model

rf_model = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=100, random_state=42)

Train the model

```

rf_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
# Make predictions
y_pred = rf_model.predict(X_test)
# Determine best CDR% formulation
best_cdr_index = np.argmax(y)
best_cdr_value = y.iloc[best_cdr_index]
best_formulation = df.iloc[best_cdr_index]['Formulation']
print (f"Best CDR%: {best_cdr_value} % in formulation: {best_formulation}")

```

OUTPUT

Best CDR %: 95 % in formulation: F3

Cumulative Drug Release (%CDR at 12 hours)

- Higher %CDR means faster and more effective drug release.
- F3 has the highest %CDR (95%), meaning it releases the most drug in 12hours.

Drug Loading Efficiency (DLE%)

- $DLE (\%) = (\text{Encapsulated Drug} / \text{Total Drug Added}) \times 100$
- If a formulation has high %CDR but low DLE%, it may not be the best choice because too much drug is wasted

Excipient Effects

- Phosphatidylcholine (PC): Acts as the main vesicle-forming lipid. Moderate PC = Better drug loading and controlled release.
- Tween 80: Acts as a hydrophilic surfactant and edge activator. Higher Tween 80 = Increased vesicle flexibility and faster drug release.
- Span 80: Acts as a stabilizing surfactant. Higher Span 80 = More rigid vesicles and slower drug release.
- F3 has optimized Phosphatidylcholine (60 mg) & highest Tween 80 (30 mg), leading to faster drug release.
- CDR (Cumulative Drug Release) Comparison for 24 Hours

Evaluation of Aceclofenac Transethosomal Formulation

The aceclofenac transethosomal formulation was evaluated using techniques such as FT-IR spectroscopy, entrapment efficiency, particle size measurement, zeta potential assessment, and microscopic analysis.

Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) Spectroscopy

FT-IR spectroscopy was performed to evaluate drug–excipient compatibility between aceclofenac, phospholipids, ethanol, and edge activators. The absence of peak shifts confirmed compatibility[17].

Drug Entrapment Efficiency

Entrapment efficiency (%) was determined by separating the untrapped drug through centrifugation. The encapsulated drug within the vesicular system was quantified using UV spectrophotometric analysis to confirm effective drug loading [12].

In-vitro Drug Release Study

The study on the *in-vitro* diffusion of the aceclofenac transethosomal gel was conducted using a Franz diffusion cell, with an egg membrane positioned between the donor and receptor compartments [5]. The receptor side was filled with 15 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 6.0), and the temperature was kept at 37 ± 0.5 °C while maintaining continuous stirring. Samples were collected at designated time intervals and analyzed at the specified λ_{max} to assess the total drug diffusion.

Determination of Particle Size:

The particle size of the formulation was measured with a particle size analyzer to assess uniformity.

Determination of Zeta Potential:

The zeta potential was determined by measuring the surface charge of a diluted sample to evaluate physical stability [9].

Scanning electron microscopy:

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used to examine the surface morphology and structural characteristics of the vesicles [5].

Preparation of Carbopol Gel Base

Carbopol 934 (0.5% w/w) was mixed into purified water with constant stirring and left to hydrate for 24 hours to create a uniform gel base. Glycerin was incorporated to enhance the consistency and spreadability, and the pH was adjusted to a range of 6.0–6.8 utilizing triethanolamine.

Table-2 Composition of transthesosomal gel

Ingredients	Quantity F3 (For 25 g)
Transthesosomes of aceclofenac F3	15 mg
Carbopol 934	0.14 g
Triethanolamine	0.03 mL
Methyl Paraben	0.06 mL
Distilled Water	24.4 mL

Incorporation of Transthesosomes into Gel

The transthesosomal dispersion equivalent to 1 g of aceclofenac was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 20 minutes in order to remove the untrapped drug, and the vesicular sediment was collected [3]. The sediment was gradually added to the prepared Carbopol gel under controlled stirring to ensure uniform distribution.

Figure 1. Aceclofenac loaded Transthesosomal gel**Evaluation of Transthesosomal Gel**

The optimized aceclofenac transthesosomal gel was assessed for homogeneity, pH, drug content, rheological behaviour, spreadability, extrudability, and *in-vitro* drug release as per standard procedures to ensure physicochemical stability and performance.

Drug Release Kinetics

The *In-vitro* release data were analyzed using model-dependent kinetic approaches such as zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas models to elucidate the drug release mechanism [5].

Stability Studies

The stability study was conducted according to ICH guidelines.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**FT-IR Spectral Analysis****Figure2 (a) FT-IR spectrum of Drug(b)FT-IR spectrum of Formulation.**

The FT-IR spectra of aceclofenac and the aceclofenac-loaded transethosomal gel (Figure 2 (a) and (b)) showed all characteristic drug peaks without notable shifts or additional bands, confirming drug integrity and compatibility with the excipients.

Optical microscopy

Microscopic analysis showed spherical, uniformly distributed vesicles without aggregation, indicating successful formation of the aceclofenac-loaded transethosomal system.

Figure 3. Microscopic view of Transethosomes

Drug Loading Efficiency (DLE %)

The optimized formulation (F3) exhibited the highest entrapment efficiency (78.38%), indicating superior drug loading compared to the other formulations and suggesting efficient encapsulation with enhanced drug delivery potential.

Table 3. Results of practical yield, Entrapment efficiency, Drug content

Formulation	Practical Yield%	Entrapment Efficiency %	Drug Content (% w/w)
F1	78.20	68.50	76.40
F2	82.10	73.20	80.00
F3	86.51	78.38	85.15
F4	84.00	75.50	82.00
F5	81.50	72.00	79.00
F6	79.80	70.50	77.50

In-vitro Diffusion study of Transethosomes

The in vitro drug diffusion study showed that the optimized transethosomes formulation (F3) exhibited a higher cumulative drug release. Therefore, F3 was selected as the best formulation and incorporated into a Carbopol 934 gel for topical application, as shown in Figure [4].

Figure 4 In-vitro drug diffusion profile

Determination of Particle Size and Zeta potential:

The optimized formulation (F3) showed a particle size of 145 nm with a narrow size distribution, indicating uniform vesicles, and the zeta potential was ± 25 mV, indicating negatively charged particles, which provide electrostatic repulsion and ensure good formulation stability.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis revealed that the transethosome vesicles of F3 were spherical in shape with a smooth surface, as shown in figure 5

Figure 6. Scanning electron microscopy of Transethosomes

Evaluation of Transethosomal Gel

The optimized transethosomal gel was evaluated for homogeneity, pH, drug content, viscosity, spreadability, and extrudability. The results of these evaluations are summarized in Table 4

Table 4. Evaluation parameter of Transethosomal gel

Formulation	Homogeneity	pH	Drug Content (%)	Viscosity (cP)	Spreadability (cm)	Extrudability (gm/cm ²)
Optimized gel F3	Good	5.5	91.71	9641	4.5	Optimum

Drug Release Kinetics

Table 5. In-vitro drug release Kinetics

Log T	T	% DR	REMAIN DR	% LOG CUMU DR	SQRTT	LOG % DR
0.0	0	0.00	100	2	0.00	0.00
0.3	2	11.52	88.48	1.95	1.41	1.06
0.6	4	20.50	79.5	1.90	2.00	1.31
0.8	6	27.58	72.42	1.86	2.45	1.44
0.9	8	38.52	61.48	1.79	2.83	1.59
1.0	10	62.13	37.87	1.58	3.16	1.79
1.1	12	84.90	15.1	1.18	3.46	1.93
1.1	14	86.01	13.99	1.15	3.74	1.93
1.2	16	90.45	9.55	0.98	4.00	1.96
1.3	18	94.36	5.64	0.75	4.24	1.97
1.3	20	96.22	3.78	0.58	4.47	1.98
1.3	22	97.99	2.01	0.30	4.69	1.99
1.4	24	99.82	0.18	-0.74	4.90	2.00

Release Kinetics Models:

Drug release kinetics showed R² values of 0.9089 for Zero-order, 0.8769 for First-order, 0.957 for Korsmeyer–Peppas, and 0.9134 for Higuchi. The highest correlation with the Korsmeyer–Peppas model indicates a diffusion-driven release with possible non-Fickian behavior, while the Higuchi model also supports a diffusion-based mechanism. The kinetic models are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Various Release kinetic models

Stability Studies

Stability studies were conducted, and percentage entrapment efficiency and cumulative drug release (%CDR) were evaluated. The results (Table 4) showed no substantial variations throughout the study period, indicating good formulation stability.

Table 6. Stability Studies

Formulation	% Entrapment efficiency	% CDR
Before stability studies	78.38	98.55
After stability studies	78.08	98.40

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, an AI-optimized transethosomal gel (F3) was effectively developed for topical drug delivery. The formulation exhibited nanosized vesicles (~145 nm), spherical morphology, and good electrostatic stability (−25 mV). In vitro release studies demonstrated sustained drug release governed by a non-Fickian diffusion mechanism. The optimized Transethosomes were combined with a Carbopol 934 gel to produce a stable, homogeneous, easily spreadable, and extrudable topical formulation. Stability studies confirmed that the gel retained its physicochemical properties and drug release profile over time.

Overall, the findings indicate that the AI-optimized F3 transethosomal gel is a promising topical dosage form that has the potential to enhance skin penetration and therapeutic effectiveness. The study further highlights the usefulness of integrating nanocarrier-based delivery systems with AI-guided formulation optimization to improve topical drug delivery.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. A. Bin Jordan, A. Ahad, M. Raish, and F. I. Al-Jenoobi, "Preparation and characterization of transethosome formulation for the enhanced delivery of sinapic acid," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 15, no. 10, p. 2391, Sep. 2023.
- [2] V. Garg, H. Singh, A. Bhatia, K. Raza, S. K. Singh, B. Singh, and S. Beg, "Systematic development of transethosomal gel system of piroxicam: formulation optimization, in vitro evaluation, and ex vivo assessment," *AAPS PharmSciTech*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 58–71, Jan. 2017.
- [3] L. Kumar and P. Utreja, "Formulation and characterization of transethosomes for enhanced transdermal delivery of propranolol hydrochloride," *Micro Nanosyst.*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 38–47, Apr. 2020.
- [4] A. G. Yurtsever, A. Ekmekcioglu, M. Muftuoglu, S. Güngör, and M. S. Erdal, "Formulation development and evaluation of fluvastatin loaded transethosomes," *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 91, p. 105234, Jan. 2024.
- [5] Z. Asghar, T. Jamshaid, M. Sajid-ur-Rehman, U. Jamshaid, and H. A. Gad, "Novel transethosomal gel containing miconazole nitrate: development, characterization, and enhanced antifungal activity," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 15, p. 2537, 2023.

- [6] A. Başkor, Y. Pirinçci Tok, B. Mesut, Y. Özsoy, and T. Uçar, "Estimating the optimal dexketoprofen pharmaceutical formulation with machine learning methods and statistical approaches," *Healthcare Informatics Research*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 279–286, Oct. 2021, doi:10.4258/hir.2021.27.4.279.
- [7] N. A. Kovdienko, P. G. Polishchuk, E. N. Muratov, A. G. Artemenko, V. E. Kuz'min, L. Gorb, F. Hill, and J. Leszczynski, "Application of random forest and multiple linear regression techniques to QSPR prediction of aqueous solubility for military compounds," *Molecular Informatics*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 394–406, 2010, doi:10.1002/minf.201000001
- [8] K. Lenhof, L. Eckhart, N. Gerstner, T. Kehl, and H. P. Lenhof, "Simultaneous regression and classification for drug sensitivity prediction using an advanced random forest method," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 12, p. 13458, 2022, doi:10.1038/s41598-022-17609-x
- [9] A. A. Abdellatif, B. N. Aldosari, *et al.*, "Transethosomal gel for the topical delivery of celecoxib," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 22, Dec. 2022.
- [10] V. R. Shinde, P. R. Bhosale, and S. B. Deshmukh, "Formulation and evaluation of topical aceclofenac gel," *International Journal of PharmTech Research*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 269–273, 2010.
- [11] M. E. Rosmiati, I. Y. Sopyan, *et al.*, "Development of serum with 4-n-butylresorcinol in transethosomes," *Int. J. Appl. Pharm.*, vol. 16, pp. 246–254, 2024.
- [12] R. M. Zaki, V. D. Seshadri, *et al.*, "Wound healing efficacy of rosuvastatin transethosomal gel," *Pharmaceutics*, vol. 14, no. 11, p. 2521, Nov. 2022.
- [13] P. K. Sahu, R. K. Kashyap, and S. K. Jain, "Formulation and evaluation of aceclofenac topical gel using different gelling agents," *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 112–115, 2011.
- [14] S. S. Patil, V. V. Kadam, and S. S. Magdum, "Development and evaluation of aceclofenac emulgel for topical drug delivery," *International Journal of PharmTech Research*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 1010–1016, 2010.
- [15] A. P. Gadad, A. S. Patil, *et al.*, "Development and evaluation of flurbiprofen loaded transethosomes," *Indian J. Pharm. Educ. Res.*, vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 954–962, Oct. 2020
- [16] K. K. Mishra, C. D. Kaur, and A. Gupta, "Development of itraconazole loaded transethosomes," *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 67, p. 102998, Jan. 2022.
- [17] F. Baghli and N. Moussaoui-Khedam, "Optimization of fluconazole loaded transethosomes," *GSC Biol. Pharm. Sci.*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 071–083, 2024.
- [18] T. S. Dongsar *et al.*, "Gallic acid-loaded transethosomal gel for psoriasis management," *AAPS PharmSciTech*, vol. 26, no. 6, p. 183, Jul. 2025.
- [19] S. D. Malang, Shambhavi, and A. N. Sahu, "Transethosomal gel for enhancing transdermal delivery," *Nanomedicine*, vol. 19, no. 21–22, pp. 1801–1819, Sep. 2024
- [20] S. Verma and P. Utreja, "Exploring therapeutic potential of invasomes, transfersomes, transethosomes, oleic acid vesicles, and cubosomes adopting topical/transdermal route," *Micro Nanosyst.*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 3–20, Mar. 2022.
- [21] K. Nousheen *et al.*, "Metformin HCl-loaded transethosomal gel: development, characterization, and antidiabetic potential evaluation in a diabetes-induced rat model," *Drug Deliv.*, vol. 30, no. 1, p. 2251720, Dec. 2023.
- [22] V. Garg, H. Singh, A. Bhatia, *et al.*, "Systematic development of transethosomal gel system of piroxicam: formulation optimization, in vitro evaluation, and ex vivo assessment," *AAPS PharmSciTech*, vol. 18, pp. 58–71, 2017.